

EFFECT OF HYDRO-PRIMING AND INCUBATION METHOD ON SEEDLING ESTABLISHMENT OF RICE VARIETY CV. BRRI DHAN 29

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Seed Laboratory, Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. The study comprised of two experiments. There were seven hydro-priming treatments in the 1st experiment *viz.*, 0 hour (control), 12 hours, 24 hours, 36 hours, 48 hours, 60 hours and 72 hours priming. The 2nd experiment comprised nine treatments *viz.*, 0 hour priming and 0 hours incubation (control), primed for 36 hours, primed for 36 hours plus 24 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 30 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 36 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 42 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 48 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 54 hours incubation and primed for 36 hours plus 60 hours incubation. The experiments were laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications. Results of the 1st experiment showed that priming treatments significantly influenced the germination and all the growth parameters of rice seedlings. 36 hours priming gave the highest germination percentage (86.75), vigor index (11.60), shoot length (9.30 cm) and shoot fresh weight (0.65 g), root length (7.6 cm), root fresh weight (0.50 g), root dry weight (0.1375 g). It also took the lowest time (7.50 days) for total germination (mean germination time). Result of the 2nd experiment revealed that 36 hours primed plus 30 hours incubation gave the highest value of germination percentage (97.25), vigor index (16.35), shoot length (12.45 cm), root length (8.60 cm), shoot fresh weight (1.09g), shoot dry weight (0.30 g), root fresh weight (0.85 g), root dry weight (0.25 g). It also took the lowest time (6.20 days) for total germination time (mean germination time). Non-primed seed took the highest time for total germination (mean germination time).

Key words: Hydro Priming, incubation, rice, seedling establishment

INTRODUCTION

Quality seed is one of the important factors for the production of rice when a good seed of a good variety gives good stand establishment, it ensures a good harvest. Seed quality is a multiple concept comprising several components (Thomson, 1979) like germination capacity, viability, vigor, moisture content and seed health etc. Quality seed ensures quality seedling. It is an important and obligatory input to maintain optimum growth and better grain yield for modern rice varieties (BRRI, 2006). But optimum crop stand establishment is the pre-requisite for successful rice production. Rice often fails to establish quickly and uniformly, leading to decreased yield, because of poor plant population. Moisture is the basic requirement for rice seed germination and essential for enzyme activity. Seedling that germinate faster and grow rapidly are able to produce sufficient deep root system before the seed bed dried out and harden and these seedlings have enough competitive ability against weed and seedling diseases. When seeds are sown, they have to absorb water from the soil which takes long time before germination. If this time could be reduced by soaking the seed before sowing, germination happens more quickly, resulting healthier crop. Seeds sown at low moisture condition will not germinate unless subsequent moisture is available. At this situation seed priming can be a simple solution towards stand establishment (Harris *et al.*, 2002). Good seedling establishment is an important constrain to crop production in semi-arid tropics (Itabari *et al.*, 1993; Harris, D., 1999). Priming in these regions have been reported to increase emergence, more vigorous plants, better drought tolerance, earlier maturing, higher grain yield (Harris, D., 1999, Harris *et al.*, 2000, 2001). Seed priming techniques are being used in many parts of the world to reduce the germination time, to get synchronized germination, improve germination rate and better seedling establishment in many field crops like rice (Lee and Kim, 1999, 2000; Basra *et al.*, 2003, 2004; Farooq *et al.*, 2004), wheat, maize (Aquilla and Tritoo, 1990; Basra *et al.*, 2002). Hydropriming practically ensured rapid and uniform germination and it had high potential in improving field emergence and ensured early flowering and harvesting under stress condition, especially in dry areas (Singh, 1995 and Shivankar *et al.*, 2003).

The above discussion indicates that priming is an effective tool for rapid and uniform seedling emergence. However, methods for priming of rice have not yet been developed in Bangladesh. Hence, the present study was undertaken to investigate the effects of priming and incubation on seed germination and seedling establishment of rice with the objectives of selecting the best seed priming technique and finding out suitable incubation period of seed for direct seeding in dry bed direct seeded (DBDS) system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Seed Laboratory, Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from July to December 2011 to study the effect of priming (hydropriming and priming plus incubation) on germination and growth of rice seedling cv. BRRI dhan29. There were seven hydro-priming treatments used in the 1st experiment viz., 0 hour (control), 12 hours, 24 hours, 36 hours, 48 hours, 60 hours and 72 hours priming and in the 2nd experiment nine priming treatments along with incubation were used viz., 0 hour priming and 0 hours incubation (control), primed for 36 hours, primed for 36 hours plus 24 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 30 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 36 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 42 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 48 hours incubation, primed for 36 hours plus 54 hours incubation and primed for 36 hours plus 60 hours incubation. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications. Seeds of BRRI dhan29 were collected from the Bangladesh Agriculture Development Corporation, Modhupur farm. Five hundred gram rice seeds were soaked in distilled, cool water for 0 hours, 12 hours, 24 hours, 36 hours, 48 hours, 60 hours and 72 hours separately as per treatments. Soaked seeds were dried at room temperature and were used in the further tests. For germination and other tests, plastic pots (22 cm diameter and 10 cm depth) were filled with 2 kg of soil which was collected from the Agronomy Field Laboratory. The amount of water held by the soil was calculated according to Piper (1950). One hundred seeds were sown in each of 28 pots for 1st experiment and 36 pots for 2nd experiment. Field capacity of the soil was maintained by supplying tap water manually. The data on germination percentage, mean germination time, vigor index, shoot length, shoot dry weight, root length and root dry weight were recorded. The daily record of germinated seed was taken up to 14 days from setting up of the test. For each priming treatments, germination percentage was calculated using the recommended formula. The mean germination time was calculated following Godchild *et al.* (1971). Daily count on germination of seed was taken to calculate seedling vigor index using the formula given by Maguire (1962). Seedling shoot and root length was recorded at 15 days after sowing. The shoot and root length of the seedlings were dried in an electric oven maintaining 72^o C temperature for 48 hours. Dry weights of shoot and root were measured accordingly. The collected data were analyzed statistically following the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) technique and the significance of the mean differences were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) (Gomez and Gomez, 1984) using a statistical computer package program MSTAT-C (Russell, 1986).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of hydro-priming on germination and growth parameters

Germination percentage

Germination percentage was significantly influenced by hydro-priming treatments (Table 1). The highest germination percentage (86.75) was found for 36 hours priming while the lowest was observed in control treatment. The results clearly showed that more germination advantages of the rice seed could be achieved by priming under field capacity. The result of the present study was in agreement with Lee *et al.* (1998) and Basra *et al.* (2005).

Mean germination time

The priming treatments had significant effect on mean germination time (days) of rice seed (Table 1). The highest value was noted in the control (8.20 days) and it was followed 12 hours. Minimum mean germination time was noted in hydro-primed for 36 hours and it was followed by 48 hours and 60 hours. The results revealed that priming enhanced rapid germination of seed compared to non-primed seed. This significant enhancement in germination might cause by enhancement of the amylase activity that is positively correlated

with the reserved mobilization and mean germination rate in rice (Lee and Kim, 2000). The results revealed that primed rice seed emerged faster and decreased the mean germination time. Similar results were also found by Harris *et al.* (2001) and Lee *et al.* (1998)

Table 1. Effect of hydro-priming treatments on germination and growth parameters of BRRI dhan29

Treatments	Germination (%)	Mean germination time (day)	Vigor index	Shoot length (cm)	Shoot dry weight (g)	Root length (cm)	Root dry weight (g)
72 hours priming	85.00 ab	7.90 ab	11.25ab	9.14 a	0.13 bc	7.28abc	0.095ab
60 hours priming	85.00 ab	7.80 ab	11.30ab	9.18 a	0.15 b	7.42 ab	0.110 ab
48 hours priming	84.25 abc	7.75 ab	11.35 ab	9.20 a	0.15 ab	7.40 ab	0.120ab
36 hours priming	86.75 a	7.50 b	11.60 a	9.30 a	0.16 a	7.60 a	0.137 a
24 hours priming	83.25abc	8.10 a	10.80 bc	8.15 b	0.14bc	7.40 ab	0.090ab
12 hours priming	82.75 bc	8.15 a	10.60 c	7.600 c	0.13 c	7.12 bc	0.090 ab
Control	80.75 c	8.20 a	10.20 c	7.350 c	0.11 d	7.05 c	0.077 b
LSD _(0.05)	3.33	0.441	0.573	0.494	0.015	0.297	0.046
Level of significance	*	*	**	**	*	**	*
CV%	2.70	3.79	3.54	3.93	14.13	2.77	24.60

In column figures with same letters or without letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly as per DMRT.

** = Significant at 1% level of probability,

* = Significant at 5% level of probability

Vigor index

Priming treatments significantly influenced the vigor index (Table 1). The highest vigor index was obtained from 36 hours priming. The lowest vigor index was obtained in control and 12 hours priming. The vigor index increase might be related to reduction of imbibition lag time for priming treatments (Bradford, 1986). Priming also causes physiological and bio-chemical changes in seed during the seed treatments and metabolic activities increased amylase activity, thus resulted in higher vigor index. The result showed that priming increased the vigor index of seed. These results were similar to those of Harris *et al.* (2000), Lee and Kim (2000) and Basra *et al.* (2003).

Seedling shoot length

Shoot length of rice seedling was affected significantly due as a result of hydropriming treatments (Table 1). The shoot length of rice seedling for different treatments ranged between 9.30 cm to 7.35 cm. The highest shoot length was found with seed primed for 36 hours treatment followed by 48 hours & 60 hours. On the other hand, the lowest shoot length (7.35 cm) value was found with non-primed seed. The result of the present study clearly showed that hydropriming enhanced shoot length of rice for soil at field capacity condition. The similar results were also found by Tongma *et al.* (2001) and Farooq *et al.* (2006).

Seedling shoot dry weight

Significant variations were observed for shoot dry weight due to different hydropriming treatments (Table 1). The highest shoot dry matter accumulation (0.165g) per 10 seedlings was measured for 36 hours followed by 48 hours. The lowest dry matter accumulation (0.115 g) per 10 seedlings was found for non-primed seed followed by 12 hours priming.

Seedling root length

The effect of hydropriming on seedling root length of rice seedling was significant at 1 % (Table 1). The highest root length (7.60 cm) was measured for seed hydropriming for 36 hours. The lowest root length (7.05 cm) was recorded for non-primed seed. The roots of primed seedlings were more fibrous. The results of the present study clearly showed that root length increase of rice seedling could be obtained by priming at field capacity level. These results were similar to those of Harris *et al.* (2000), Lee and Kim (2000) and Basra *et al.* (2003).

Seedling root dry weight

The root dry mass of rice seedling was affected significantly when hydropriming treatments were applied at field capacity condition. The root dry mass of rice seedling for different treatments ranged between 0.077 g to 0.137 g (Table 1). The highest root fresh dry mass was found with seed primed for 36 hours. It was statistically identical with 48 hours and 60 hours hydropriming treatments. On the other hand, the lowest root fresh weight (0.077 g) value was found with non-primed seed. The result of the present study showed that priming enhanced root dry mass of rice seedling at field capacity condition. Similar results were also found by Tongma *et al.* (2001) and Farooq *et al.* (2006).

Priming plus incubation effect of rice on germination and growth parameters

Germination percentage

Germination percentage of the rice seed was significantly influenced by priming plus incubation treatments (Table 2). The highest germination percentage was 97.25 found in seed priming for 36 hours plus incubation for 30 hours. The lowest germination percentage was found in control treatment. The results revealed that priming along with incubation enhanced rapid germination of seed compared to non-primed seed. The result of the present study was in agreement with that of Lee *et al.* (1998) and Basra *et al.* (2005). Over priming and incubation delayed and poor germination of seed. Lee and Kim (1999, 2000).

Mean germination time

Priming for 36 hours plus incubation treatments had significant effect on mean germination time (days) for rice seedlings for soil at field capacity moisture conditions (Table 2). The mean germination time of seed for different treatments ranged between 7.32 to 6.20 days. The highest mean germination time was noted in the control treatment i.e. it was after 36 hours priming only. However, the rest of the treatments resulted in lower mean germination time than the control and minimum mean germination time was noted in seeds hydropriming for 36 hours plus 30 hours incubation. The results revealed that 36 hours priming with incubation enhanced rapid germination of seed compared with non-primed seed.

Table 2. Effect of seed hydropriming plus incubation treatments on on germination and growth parameters of BRRI dhan29

Treatments	Germination (%)	Mean germination time (day)	Vigor index	Shoot length (cm)	Shoot dry weight (g)	Root length (cm)	Root dry weight (g)
T ₁	94.25 ab	6.685 b	15.45 bc	10.35 c	0.2300 bc	6.350 d	0.1300 b
T ₂	94.25 ab	6.465 bc	15.80 abc	10.40 c	0.2000 c	6.420 d	0.1100 b
T ₃	95.00 a	6.750 b	15.96 ab	11.40 b	0.2200 c	7.300 c	0.1200 b
T ₄	97.25 a	6.200 c	16.35 a	12.45 a	0.3000 a	8.600 a	0.2500 a
T ₅	96.25 a	6.410 bc	16.12 ab	12.30 a	0.2800 a	8.100 ab	0.2300 a
T ₆	94.50 ab	6.520 bc	16.10 ab	12.15 a	0.2700 ab	7.800 bc	0.2300 a
T ₇	91.75 bc	6.550 bc	15.20 c	10.50 c	0.2200 c	7.510 bc	0.1300 b
T ₈	89.00 cd	7.110 a	13.65 d	9.190 d	0.1800 cd	6.300 d	0.1200 b
T ₉	86.20 d	7.320 a	12.70 e	8.182 e	0.1500 d	6.020 d	0.09000 b
LSD _(0.05)	2.87	0.346	0.644	0.571	0.046	0.617	0.046
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV%	2.13	3.59	2.91	3.66	13.09	5.95	15.34

In column figures with same letters or without letters do not differ significantly where as figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly as per DMRT. ** = Significant at 1% level of probability

T₁ = 36 hours primed plus 60 hours incubation, T₂ = 36 hours primed plus 54 hours incubation, T₃ = 36 hours primed plus 48 hours incubation, T₄ = 36 hours primed plus 42 hours incubation, T₅ = 36 hours primed plus 36 hours incubation, T₆ = 36 hours primed plus 30 hours incubation, T₇ = 36 hours primed plus 24 hours incubation, T₈ = 36 hours primed only, T₉ = Control

Vigor index

Priming plus incubation treatments significantly influenced the vigor index of rice (Table 2). The highest vigor index was obtained from 36 hours priming plus 30 hours incubation. The lowest vigor index was obtained in control. The vigor index increase might be related to reduction of imbibition lag time for priming treatments (Bradford, 1986). Priming plus incubation also causes physiological and bio-chemical changes in seed during the seed treatments and metabolic activities increases amylase activity, and thus result in higher vigor index (Lee and Kim). The result showed that priming increased the vigor index of seed. This result is similar to that of Harris *et al.* (2000), Lee and Kim (2000) and Basra *et al.* (2003).

Seedling shoot length

Shoot length of rice seedling was affected significantly by priming plus incubation treatments (Table 2). The shoot length of rice seedling for different treatments ranged between 8.182 cm to 12.45 cm. The highest shoot length was found with seed priming for 36 hours plus 30 hours incubation. On the other hand, the lowest shoot length (8.182 cm) values were found with non-primed seed. The results of the present study clearly showed that root length increase of rice seedling could be obtained by priming at field capacity. Similar results were also found by Tongma *et al.* (2001) and Farooq *et al.* (2006b).

Seedling shoot dry weight

Significant variations were observed for shoot dry weight due to different priming plus incubation treatments. The shoot dry weight of rice seedlings for different treatments ranged between 0.15 g to 0.30 g per 10 seedlings. The highest shoot dry matter accumulation (0.30 g) was measured for 36 hours priming plus 30 hours incubation treatments. The lowest dry matter accumulation (0.15 g) was found for non-primed seed.

Seedling root length

The effect of priming plus incubation treatments on seedling root length of rice was significant at 1% (Table 2). The highest root length (8.60 cm) was measured for 36 hours priming plus incubation for 30 hours. The lowest root length was found with non-primed seed. The roots of seedlings at this soil moisture condition were more fibrous. Over priming and incubation period hampered the seedling growth and development (Lee and Kim, 1999, 2000).

Seedling root dry weight

The root dry mass of rice seedling was affected significantly due to priming plus incubation treatments for field capacity condition (Table 2). The root dry mass of rice seedling for different treatments ranged between 0.09 g to 0.25 g per 10 seedlings. The highest root fresh dry mass was found with seed primed for 36 hours priming plus 30 hours incubation. Twenty four hours priming plus 36 hours incubation treatments were statically identical with 36 hours priming plus 42 hours incubation. On the other hand, the lowest root fresh weight (0.09 g) was obtained from non-primed seed and it was followed 36 hours priming plus 54 hours incubation. The result of the present study showed that priming enhanced root dry mass of rice seedling at field capacity condition.

CONCLUSION

From above results it could be concluded that, seed priming for 36 hours in combination with incubation treatment enhanced faster germination and vigorous growth of rice seedlings. These findings may be further tried in field experimentation for validation through yield trials before packaging technologies in the farmer's field.

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